

D8.1: Report on the Dissemination and Communication Plan

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ABSTRACT:	<p>This report presents the central strategy of dissemination and communication of XR4HUMAN. In addition, it describes in detail the tools and channels, which will be used to make the dissemination, communication effective and efficient, targeting at the maximisation of the project's impact. The success of the XR4HUMAN project, being a Coordination and Support Action, heavily depends on the quality of dissemination and communication. The efficiency of these two activities increases the visibility of XR4HUMAN findings and outputs and facilitates the engagement strategy and plan, explicated in D1.1. This in turn is largely dependent on the extent to which its communications are received and acted upon by our specific types of beneficiaries as described in the DoA.</p>
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1 Introduction

1.1. About the project

eXtended Reality (XR) technologies have within a few years moved from lab-based research to a common-place consumer item. Indeed, the benefits of and the possibilities that XR technologies offer to promote and enhance are prolific. As with other emerging technologies, however, the use and eventual ubiquity of XR technologies bring with them potential risks that have not existed before. Of particular importance are new ethical and associated safety, privacy, security challenges and interoperability issues that needs to be urgently considered. Developing the foundations to ensure that Europe is sufficiently equipped to leverage these opportunities through skilful navigation of new challenges is the rationale for XR4HUMAN.

The MAIN OBJECTIVE of the project is to co-create living guidance on ethical and related policy, regulatory, governance, and interoperability issues of XR technologies within a European community of practice. This main objective will be operationalized through the following specific objectives:

- **EXPLORE** (i) ethical issues; and (ii) related regulatory and governance issues;
- **GUIDE** companies and regulators through (i) Interoperability Guidance Document; (ii) a European Code of Conduct for Equitable, Inclusive, and Human-Centered XR Technologies; (iii) recording and demonstrating the practical application of the XR Code of Conduct;
- **EQUIP** companies and regulators with an online repository of test cases to allow developers to demonstrate evidence of adherence to best practices;
- **EQUIP** and **GUIDE** users through a rating system and educational materials;
- **ENGAGE** companies and other stakeholders (i) to enhance the uptake of the XR Code of Conduct, the Guidance for Interoperability, and the empowerment of end-users; and (ii) to establish a permanent digital European Forum to facilitate stakeholder dialogue on issues of ethics and interoperability.

1.2. About this deliverable

The present report describes the Dissemination and Communication Plan of XR4HUMAN project and contains details on all types of dissemination and communication activities through which we foresee to maximize visibility of the project's results and engagement of relevant stakeholders. The Dissemination and Communication Plan ensures communication between the XR4HUMAN beneficiaries and all relevant stakeholders to achieve the highest possible visibility.

The outcomes of WP8 will directly influence and be influenced by the work of all the other WPs, especially of WP1. WP8 will boost visibility of the project's findings, assist European XR companies and other stakeholder engagement, maintain the continuous and strong interaction between the members of the permanent digital European Forum (WP1, ENGAGE: Stakeholder Engagement and Horizontal Coordination); disseminate and communicate the online repository of test cases which will allow developers to demonstrate evidence of adherence to best practices (WP6, ENGAGE and GUIDE: Demonstration and Validation, including online platform of test cases); and facilitate the use of rating system and the educational and informational toolbox for users (WP7, EQUIP and GUIDE: Empowering end-users through a rating system and an educational toolbox).

Main objective

ENGAGE: Engage European XR companies and other stakeholders towards the uptake of the XR Code of Conduct, the Guidance for Interoperability, and the empowerment of end-users.

Sub- Objectives

- Dissemination and communication XR4HUMAN's engagement procedures, findings, and outcomes.
- Exploitation of XR4HUMAN's outputs in a structured and efficient way.
- Contribution to WP1 to facilitate the project's stakeholder engagement procedures.
- Optimize uptake and exploitation of XR4HUMAN's outcomes to boost their sustainability.

2 Conceptual issues

XR4HUMAN work programme will be carried out by nine work packages (WPs), two of which (WP1 and WP8) will have to engage with stakeholders. WP1 will have to recruit stakeholders and create the conditions for a sustainable deep interaction and co-creation of XR4HUMAN outputs, while WP8 will carry out the dissemination and communication activities. Though these two broad types of activities are different, there are overlaps between them. For this reason, NTUA (WP8 leader) and XR4Europe (WP1 leader) have interacted during the first months of the project, to develop strategies for recruitment (referred to as 'stakeholder engagement' in D1.1), dissemination, and communication to produce deliverables that are complementary, and to avoid duplication of work. This is reflected by the fact that NTUA has been involved in the drafting of D1.1, while XR4Europe has reviewed D8.1.

The result of this interaction is the way that WP1 and WP8 partners conceptualise recruitment, dissemination, and communication, as well as the target groups of these three distinct, but organically interacting activities. Specifically, these activities are on the same continuum of the engagement spectrum, which are differentiated by the nature of the interaction (see section 2.1). In addition, based on the same model, we have categorised the types of stakeholders that will be targeted primarily for communication, dissemination, and recruitment, in the context of the different WPs or types of outputs (please see section 2.2).

2.1. The continuum of engagement

We conceptualise the continuum of engagement taking inspiration from the International Association for Public Participation that identifies five different levels of stakeholder engagement that are listed in **Table 1**. This table, which also is referred to in D1.1, demonstrates the different stakeholder engagement methods that will be used for collecting stakeholders' views and opinions or involving them in specific decision-making. The different engagement approaches reflects an increase in the depth of engagement as we shift from the *Informing* approach down to the *Empowerment* approach.

Informing can be considered as an engagement approach that will be achieved by the communication and dissemination activities of WP8. The stakeholders, in this instance, are rather passive recipients of the information that will be conveyed from the dissemination and communication channels of XR4HUMAN (see **Tables 2** and **4**). The action requested from the engaged stakeholder is simply to get access to and read from, e.g., the website or social media channels of XR4HUMAN.

The *Consultation* approach requests from the engaged stakeholder to provide input, mostly remotely, as described in **Table 1**. In this case, the stakeholder is no longer passive, but it is solicited and encouraged to provide feedback, and as such, becomes a proactive player in the project. In the *Involving* and *Collaboration* approaches, the stakeholder is more deeply involved; with “deeply” it is meant that the stakeholder may have to be involved via its physical presence (or online activities) and provide more nuanced feedback, than in the case of an online survey or contributions in public documents. In these three cases, the action requested by the stakeholder is substantially more demanding than in the *Informing* approach. These three engagement approaches will be achieved by the recruitment activities of WP1 and engagement activities of the WPs that will form the programme of XR4HUMAN.

Finally, the *Empowerment* approach of XR4HUMAN could be considered as the outcome of the project. XR4HUMAN has the ambition, by involving stakeholders in the co-creation of all its outputs, to provide the conditions to empower them to influence policy making.

Table 1: The International Association for Public Participation Stakeholder Engagement (D1.1 and references therein).

Engagement approach	Overview	Main goals
<i>Informing</i> (dissemination and communication needed)	Reaching Stakeholders via websites, fact sheets, newsletters, or allowing visitors to read project discussions and inform themselves.	The level of engagement in this form is very low and suitable to engage stakeholders with low urgency, influence, importance, or interest
<i>Consulting</i> (recruitment needed)	Conducting interviews, administering surveys to gather	To elicit the views, interests, and any salient information,

	information, opening draft project documents for public comment, or using web 2.0 tools to gather ideas.	stakeholder consultations will take place
Involving (recruitment needed)	Scenario building engaging panels of experts such as the Delphi method or group model building that includes simulating policy choices, games, or role-playing.	Have a shared experience and exchange localized or specialized knowledge, overcome “he symmetry of ignorance” to learn, create a common understanding, and identify alternative choices
Collaboration (recruitment needed)	Stakeholders’ advice and recommendations will be incorporated in the final decisions to a maximum extent.	Intense engagement, creating tight bonds with stakeholders
Empowerment (outcome)	The final decision-making is in the hands of the public.	Realistically, collaboration and empowerment exist within institutional and legal parameter

2.2. Engaged stakeholders: The influence/Interest matrix

XR4HUMAN will engage, through the communication and dissemination activities the following types of stakeholders: developers of hardware and software for XR applications, researchers, members of Research Ethics committees, policy makers, legal experts, science journalists, XR technology consumers, and the public (i.e., lay people who may not be aware of or have any experience with XR technologies), as presented in the following sections. Based on their **Power** to influence, and on their **Interest** in the project's overall purpose, objectives, and outputs, their positioning on the Influence/Interest matrix will vary (**Figure 1**). This matrix categorises stakeholders in four different areas, considering the four combinations of their **Power** and **Interest**. The text in red indicates the type(s) of engagement approach that shall be followed, considering their **Power** and **Interest**.

Figure 1: The influence/interest matrix with the different levels of engagement superimposed.

The diagram is separated by the dashed curved lines into three regions. These regions determine the type of activities WP8 and WP1 will have to apply. For example, stakeholders with *low Power* and *low Interest* are going to be engaged following primarily the “Inform” engagement approach, via the application of the planned communication activities of WP8. Stakeholders with *high Power* and *high Interest* are going to be engaged following the “Inform”, “Consult”, “Involve”, and “Collaborate” engagement approaches, via the application of the planned communication, dissemination activities of WP8 and the recruitment activities of WP1.

The limits of the regions defined above are not abrupt nor strict, and that lines of continuity exist between each. For example, the passage from stakeholders with *low Interest* to those with *high Interest* is rather through a continuous increase of their Interest. As such, the diagram of **Figure 1**, must be used only as a guide, when deciding on the level of engagement.

In addition, the perceived level of *Power* and *Interest* of different types of stakeholders, in the context of XR4HUMAN, depends also on the type of output that these stakeholders are going to engage with. For example, the level of *Interest* and *Power* of users of XR technologies for the interoperability guidelines can be considered high, while their *Interest* and *Power* for the Code of Conduct for responsible XR technologies could be considered low. Accordingly, these factors have to be taken into account when deciding the communication and dissemination strategy, to be applied by WP8, but, most importantly, when deciding the extent or intensity of engagement strategy that will be applied under WP1.

3 Plan for dissemination activities

To maximize impact, XR4HUMAN's dissemination strategy lies in involving key stakeholders in its engagement activities, so that they are incentivised and ready to adhere, adopt and promote the XR4HUMAN results on a wide scale. XR4HUMAN will target different stakeholder types, to whom the consortium has already established strong links due to existing collaboration and discussions during the preparation of the proposal.

Each stakeholder type will have different needs from XR4HUMAN. The XR4HUMAN consortium has analyzed their respective stakes/needs and has developed a strategy for dissemination: this strategy has defined how to disseminate and what to disseminate for each stakeholder type. The means of dissemination have been elaborated during the preparation of the proposal and the XR4HUMAN Kick off Meeting (KoM). This report includes the suggestions of the XR4HUMAN consortium partners during the KoM. An overview of the target stakeholders, the purpose of dissemination and the specific channels and tools for dissemination are presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Dissemination strategy of XR4HUMAN.

Targeted stakeholders	Purpose of dissemination	Main channels of dissemination	Tools of dissemination
Associations of industries and Developers <i>(Business Europe, Digital Europe, Eurochambres)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote XR4HUMAN results 	Press releases	e-Articles
		XR4HUMAN conference	Oral presentations; Expert panels
		Social media	LinkedIn
Consumer Associations, Civilsociety organizations <i>(Sense About Science, ENNA, Civil Society Europe)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Recruiting in engagement events Promote XR4HUMAN results 	Engagement events	Stakeholder consultations (WP5), Online Community-Focused Platform (WP6), Experiences from stakeholders (WP7)
		XR4HUMAN website	Newsfeed, e-newsletters
		Social media	Twitter
Generalpublic [Users of XR technologies and non-users] <i>(media audiences, science</i>		Public outreach events	Oral presentations in Science Communication and Researcher’s Night events

<i>audiences, bloggers, active social media users)</i>			
Research Policy makers <i>(e.g. EC officials, members of CEI, members of STOA)</i> Legal experts <i>(e.g. members of STOA)</i> Researchers and programmers <i>(e.g. immersive health care collaboration)</i> Members of RECs <i>(e.g. members of EUREC)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruiting in engagement events • Promote XR4HUMAN results 	Engagement events	XR4HUMAN encounters (WP1), Governance debate forum (WP3), Stakeholder consultations (WP5), Online Community-Focused Platform (WP6), Experiences from stakeholders (WP7)
		Scientific publications	Peer-reviewed articles
		Social media	Twitter, LinkedIn
		Conferences	Oral/poster presentations
		Workshops	Oral presentations, participations
		Platforms	Embassy of Good Science, SOPs4RI Toolbox
Science journalists <i>(working in e-journals, e.g. Horizon Magazine)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raise awareness of XR4HUMAN's findings, • Promote XR4HUMAN results 	Press releases	e-Articles
		Downloadable material	Leaflets and/or brochures
		XR4HUMAN website	Newsfeed, e-newsletters
		Social media	Twitter, LinkedIn

This project's website (to be launched in February 2023) will serve as the intersection point for all dissemination and communication activities, with sections dedicated to the project's objectives, contribution, outputs, deliverables, and social media presence (Twitter and LinkedIn). An overview of the XR4HUMAN website structure can be found in D8.2. Regarding the main outputs of the project, the project's website will contain specific sections presenting the Interoperability Guidelines, the XR rating system and the toolbox of informational and educational materials, as well as the online repository of test cases.

Besides showcasing XR4HUMAN results, the project's website will also function as an aggregator that aims to integrate parts of existing websites from EU-funded projects that have the following types of outcomes: XR technologies in general, users oriented educational and informational material for XR Technologies, Platforms, Ethics in general (see **Table 3**). The relevance of XR4HUMAN to these projects is described by the elements presented by the title of the columns. Specifically, these projects will provide contact points with XR4HUMAN with regard Educational and informational

material, Platforms, Ethics in general, and XR Technologies. The project could potentially attract ongoing projects with a focus on the above-mentioned categories by requesting their coordinators to participate in events organised by XR4HUMAN.

Table 3: Projects XR4HUMAN is going to target for dissemination and communication purposes.

Platform	Educational material	Ethics and Integrity	XR TECHNOLOGIES	RRI
PANELFIT	XR2LEARN	iRECS	DIDYMO S-XR	RRI Tools
HEIRRI	XR4ED	PRO-RES	SHARESPACE	SUPER MoRRI
UTTER	VIRT2UE	SIENNA	SUN	NewHoRRizon
SPIRIT	HEIRRI	TechEthos	THEIA-XR-Making	-
ENTIRE	ROSIE	SOPs4RI	XRECO	-
-	ENERI	POIESIS	CORTEX2	-
-	INTEGRITY	IANUS	-	-
-	Path2Integrity	VERITAS	-	-
-	-	BEYOND	-	-
-	Winners of the HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-12		-	-

3.1 What will be disseminated?

The objectives of the plan for dissemination set specific targets on what will be disseminated. Specifically:

- Project events for communication reasons (before and after the events)
- Project events for engagement reasons (before the events)
- Project documents
- Project progress
- Regular updates on the projects
- Project findings
- Participation in conferences, workshops of other projects
- Major events in XR technologies and especially in those which will be related to ethical and regulatory issues in the field of XR Technologies, as well as Final reports of other related projects.

4 Plan for communication activities

In addition to the plan for dissemination activities, XR4HUMAN consortium partners will undertake communication activities throughout the duration of the project and, most intensely, during milestones of the project. Communication activities to promote XR4HUMAN will be an important aspect of this Coordination and Support Action, to increase visibility of the project, gain awareness of the responsible practices in the field of XR technologies and reach a wide range of stakeholders.

Through targeted and easily accessible communication activities, XR4HUMAN will ensure that stakeholders are aware of XR4HUMAN progress and findings. As part of WP8, the consortium will ensure timely and clear communication of project results to all relevant stakeholder types (**Table 4**). The main targets of communication will define the language that is going to be used; e.g. Twitter will mainly target the public, using non-technical and easy-to-understand language, while LinkedIn will mainly target developers and/or associations of industries and the language can be more technical, but avoiding sophisticated jargon.

Table 4: Overview of the communication channels of XR4HUMAN.

<p>Branding: NTUA will develop a brand identity that will be used at all XR4HUMAN dissemination and communication channels (logo, website, deliverable, oral presentation and poster presentation templates); for more information see D8.2.</p>	
<p>Website: XR4HUMAN website will be launched within February 2023 to provide up-to-date information on the project, partners, progress, goals, and events.</p>	
<p>Social media: Social media channels that will be used are Twitter and LinkedIn, to reach the public and relevant stakeholders. NTUA in collaboration with XR4Europe and USN will assess the need for an additional/alternative Social Media channel, if needed.</p>	
<p>Conferences: XR4HUMAN consortium members will participate in conferences and interact with industry and experts in the field of XR, Research Ethics, Research Integrity, and Technology Assessment. A list of relevant conferences has been compiled by XR4Europe and is part of D1.1.</p>	
<p>Workshops: XR4HUMAN participants will actively participate in other relevant EU funded project’s workshops, relevant to XR technologies, Research Ethics of disruptive technologies, and Research Integrity (Table 3).</p>	
<p>Public outreach events: XR4HUMAN partners will participate in open public events, like open lectures in science museums, participations in Researcher’s Night events and in Science Communication events (e.g. Pint of Science).</p>	
<p>Press releases: Press releases, targeting papers with national circulation written in the partners’ national languages will boost project’s communication of the latest findings</p>	

on a national scale.	
Downloadable material: Dissemination materials such as newsletters and brochures will be produced to inform all relevant stakeholders.	
Scientific publications: Peer-reviewed publications in leading scientific journals related to XR technologies, Technology Assessment, Research Ethics, Responsible Research and Innovation, and Policy making.	

Although XR4HUMAN partners' respective backgrounds and experiences differ, they all share extensive experience in online and offline communication and will use this to communicate with the XR4HUMAN stakeholders. The pre-existence of communication accounts (organizational and individual) and established networks will provide smooth and wide-reaching announcements for the project's outputs. As shown in **Table 5**, communication activities must reach specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be deemed successful. A Social Media manager has been appointed in NTUA that, in addition to keeping active XR4HUMAN's Twitter and LinkedIn accounts, will also monitor the fulfilment of KPIs and report during the WP leaders' meeting, in case corrective measures will be needed.

Table 5: Key Performance Indicators, and their proposed targets for XR4HUMAN's communication activities.

Channel	Tool	Indicator	M12	M24	M36
Website	Newsfeed	Number	15	30	60
	e-newsletters	Number	2	4	6
	Visits	Visits	250	700	2500
Socialmedia	Twitter	Followers/tweets	100/10	300/20	1000/500
		Fe-tweets/likes	100/50	300/200	500/500
	LinkedIn	Followers/posts	40/20	100/40	200/80
Scientificconfer ences	Oral/poster presentations	Participations	4	8	12
Workshops	Participation	Participations	5	10	15
Pressrelease	Newspapers	Articles	1	2	4
	e-Magazines	Articles	1	2	4
Electronicdownloa ble documents	Brochures orleaflets	Downloads	200	500	1000
Publicevents	Researcher's nights	XR4HUMAN booth	-	1	2
	Science communication events	Oral presentations	1	2	4
Scientificpublica tions	Peer-reviewed articles/Opinion	Number of publications	-	2	4

5 Next steps

The NTUA team is working to create a basis for the next steps, which have to be put into action within the next months of 2023. The plan for 2023 is as follows:

- Elaborating stakeholders'/target types' list based on the work that will be streamlined in the context of WP1
- WP8 partners will closely interact with WP1, on a continuous base, to gain insights into the stakeholder engagement methodology that has been developed in the context of Task 1.1 and is presented in D1.1 as the "Seven steps XR4HUMAN stakeholder engagement plan"
- In collaboration with USN, the project's coordinator, the project's website (due to M4, i.e. February 2023) will be fully developed and ready to be launched by NTUA within February 2023.
- Enhancement of XR4HUMAN's presence on social media channels
- Start designing the basic format of XR4HUMAN's brochures and leaflets that are due to M12 (end of October 2023)

6 Deviations from DoA

No deviations from the DoA.